

Hair Politics Rooted in Colonialism: The Impact on Students' Experiences in Ghanaian Public Schools

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This paper examines hair politics in Ghanaian public schools, exploring how colonial-era policies continue to impact students' academic experiences and cultural identity. Drawing on decolonial theory and historical analysis, the research investigates the persistent legacy of colonial hair regulations that restrict Black African students' self-expression. Through a comprehensive literature review of academic databases, historical archives, and contemporary sources, this paper traces the evolution of hair politics from precolonial educational practices to current restrictive school policies. The study reveals how existing hair regulations represent a complex intersection of historical power dynamics, cultural suppression, and educational governance. The research demonstrates how these policies marginalise students, undermining their sense of identity and inclusion within public schools. The study's distinctive contribution lies in its framing of colonial ideals imposed on Ghanaians as rooted in European sumptuary laws that acted as an ideological framework for how European colonialists subjugated Ghanaians. The findings highlight the need to reconceptualise school hair policies, positioning them as critical sites of cultural resistance and personal empowerment. This research contributes to broader discussions on decolonising educational practices and affirming students' diverse cultural identities in postcolonial contexts.

A current debate in Ghana's public school system is whether the policy on hairstyling for Black African students is a remnant of colonial rule that should be dismantled or a practical measure promoting uniformity (Antwi and Bonsu, 2024; Darkwa, 2021; Essel, 2021). This policy, which requires Black African students to maintain short, shaved hair throughout academic terms, represents a complex intersection of cultural identity, historical power dynamics, and educational governance. Ghanaian students have presented on online forums (Twitter, Reddit, and YouTube) the discrepancies in the policy's rationale while signalling their growing awareness of how current hair politics marginalise students and suppress self-expression. As students have shown discontent towards the restrictive policy (Antwi and Bonsu, 2024; Essel, 2021; Manfo, 2018), teachers and administrators continue to enforce it. This results in the need to understand the underlying assumptions of such a policy and its impact on students' academic and personal development.

While existing literature primarily traces hair regulations in Ghanaian schools to the establishment of castle schools in the Gold Coast (Antwi and Bonsu, 2024; Essah, 2008; Manfo, 2018), this paper situates these policies within a broader historical framework. It links hair regulations to the legacy of European sumptuary laws and examines how these laws influenced educational policies. In doing so, the paper extends the discussion of hair politics beyond the colonial schooling system to European legal traditions that sought to regulate social hierarchies through bodily presentation. This paper highlights how contemporary hair regulations in Ghanaian schools function as remnants of colonial control, shaping students' experiences of inclusivity within academic spaces and their overall personal development.

METHODS

This paper uses 'hair politics' as an analytical framework to examine how regulation, cultural norms and practices of Black hair in Ghanaian educational institutions have evolved from precolonial to contemporary times. Building on Ngandu-Kalenga Greensword's (2022) North American definition of hair politics as 'the ways in which hair is systemically used to determine, illustrate, and exemplify who is in charge, who may impose their will upon others, who is oppressed, and who is acknowledged' (Greensword, 2022, p. 1), this analysis extends this framework to examine Ghana's unique context. Within Ghanaian education, hair politics manifests through institutional practices that have transformed Indigenous hair traditions into sites of cultural control, national identity construction, and, more recently, decolonial

resistance. By tracing these transformations across distinct historical periods, this paper reveals how educational governance of Black hair is a manifestation of broader colonial and postcolonial power dynamics in Ghanaian society.

Given the broad historical scope of this study, it is important to acknowledge certain limitations. The vast temporal range—from pre-15th century to the present—necessitates reliance on a combination of historical reconstructions, secondary literature, and archival sources, each of which presents interpretative challenges. While this paper aims to provide a comprehensive trajectory of hair politics in Ghanaian education, the availability of historical records varies across time periods, and some gaps in documentation remain. Additionally, while this study highlights key transformations, it does not claim to exhaustively capture all regional or community-specific variations in hair practices over time. Instead, it offers a synthesised overview that foregrounds the enduring impact of colonial legacies on contemporary educational policies of Black hair.

Literature was identified using search terms like "hair politics Ghana," "traditional education practices in Ghana," and "colonial education practices in Ghana" across academic databases such as JSTOR and ERIC (Education Resource Information Center). To broaden the results, searches incorporated historical terms like 'Gold Coast' and included specific ethno-linguistic group names (e.g., Akan, Ewe, Ga). Grey literature—including blogs, online forums, dissertations, and reputable news articles—were compiled through Google Scholar and Google searches to capture contemporary local experiences. The literature review was further enriched by archival visual documentation from the Basel Missionary Archives, Cambridge University Digital Library, and the University of Bristol's Gladstone Collection, which provided photographic evidence of school children's hairstyles during the period spanning 1880-1960s.

STRUCTURE

This paper examines how hair politics rooted in colonialism impact the academic experiences of students in Ghanaian public schools. First, the discussion is situated within the framework of decolonial theory to demonstrate how colonial legacies permeate the educational practices of postcolonial societies. The role of hair in precolonial education practices is then explored, highlighting how various communities valued hairstyles as expressions of cultural education. This contrasts with the colonial era, where missionary schools, supported by colonial governments, imposed hair politics as part of efforts to suppress Indigenous practices and enforce compliance with European standards. Finally, the paper examines contemporary hair politics, revealing how these colonial-era ideologies persist in modern school regulations, often marginalising students and limiting their self-expression. Perspectives from educators will be introduced to provide insight into the challenges of reforming the current policy regarding Black African students' hairstyling. The paper concludes by synthesising these findings and suggesting areas for further research, particularly the need for policy changes that affirm the diverse identities of Ghanaian students.

EMPLOYING DECOLONIAL THEORY: A THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

Concepts And Principles

Decolonial theory focuses on the persistence of colonial power structures, emphasising the distinction between colonialism—the historical system of direct control—and coloniality – the legacy of such control in power, knowledge, and societal organisation (Ndlovu-Gatsheni, 2021 as cited in Gebremariam, 2021). Central to this critique is the recognition of how Western epistemologies have achieved global dominance, leading to the marginalising and essentialising of colonised peoples (Mbembe, 2001; Mignolo, 2022; Thiong'o, 1986). Mudimbe (1988) uniquely highlights how such essentialisation occurs even within formerly colonised communities as a result thereof. More specifically, in cases like Ghana, efforts to build national unity often relied on the idea of a single, fixed cultural identity, echoing colonial tendencies to erase difference (Adjei, 2010; Adzahlie-Mensah and Dunne, 2018; Sefa Dei, 2005).

Decolonial theorists examine how colonial power structures persist through educational practices, with an overall understanding that ideological liberation is needed to achieve true independence (Nkrumah, 1965). In *On the Postcolony*, Mbembe (2001) gives insight into how coloniality operates subtly in the daily lives and culture of postcolonial societies. Mignolo (2022) adds to the original assertion of Aníbal Quijano (2007), stating that despite political independence from colonial powers, postcolonial societies have yet to 'delink' from Eurocentric epistemologies. Frantz Fanon's (1952) ideals affirm Mignolo's concept of 'delinking', asserting that decolonisation, the dismantling of historically oppressive systems– needs to involve restructuring societal consciousness to foster self-determination. In *Decolonising the Mind*, Ngũgĩ wa Thiong'o (1986) offers a solution, showing how language functions not merely as a tool for

communication, but as a carrier of culture and a framework through which reality is understood and articulated by. By Indigeneity, he argues, communities resist Eurocentric dominance embedded in educational discourse and norms.

As It Relates to Hair Politics In Education

Hair, as a marker of cultural identity and personal expression, becomes a critical lens through which colonial legacies manifest (Omotoso, 2018; Antwi and Bonsu, 2024). Ghanaian feminist scholar and educator, Ama Ata Aidoo, agrees with this notion, writing extensively on the importance of decolonising hair politics in Ghana and its relations to cultural heritage and feminine identities (George et al., 1993). Aidoo's (2002) short story, *Her Hair Politics*, critiques the increasing use of Eurocentric wigs amongst African women, linking it to how postcolonial knowledge systems impact tradition and culture. Aidoo states that postcolonialism is influenced by “what has been lost in the process of colonisation, and what is being lost in the process of “Westernisation” (George et al., 1993, p. 305). Western epistemologies embedded in educational institutions manifest through institutional mandates like requiring Black African students to shave their heads for enrolment (Antwi and Bonsu, 2024). This latently creates a generational disconnect that ultimately reshapes aesthetic choices (Byrd and Tharps, 2014; George et al., 1993).

Decolonial theory further illuminates how institutional practices can function as a mechanism of exclusion and control (Adjei, 2007; Sefa Dei, 2005). Sefa Dei (2005) writes about how colonialism within Ghana's education system has resulted in a lack of inclusivity— or the ability to affirm ‘differences’. By examining hair regulations in Ghanaian public schools, this research interrogates how colonial epistemologies continue to shape educational practices that marginalise students' cultural identities and self-expression.

PRECOLONIAL HAIR PRACTICES: CULTURAL AUTONOMY AND IDENTITY

Figure 1. Hairdressing in West Africa. Courtesy of the Afrika Museum, Berg en Dal. Found in Sieber and Herreman, 2000.

Figure 1 shows an older woman styling a younger girl's hair while another child observes and learns the technique. This visual representation aligns with scholarly discussions on the role of hairdressing in transmitting cultural knowledge and social values (Essah, 2008). Prior to European colonisation in the 15th century, education was a community-based practice (Kwamena-Poh, 1975; Pinto, 2019), with hairdressing serving as a mechanism in teaching children about societal roles and cultural identity. Hairdressers—often trusted elders, friends, or parental figures—were not only skilled artisans but also educators, using hair styling as a medium to pass down intergenerational cultural knowledge and values to younger generations (Essah, 2008; Sieber and Herreman, 2000). Pinto (2019) notes that it was not until the arrival of European colonialists that hairdressers started to be considered “uneducated.”

Hairstyles could be worn for aesthetic purposes, but often were social indicators (Ngandu-Kalenga Greensword, 2021). In Akan and Ewe ethnolinguistic societies, hairdressing was so integral to social order and identity that uncut hair—associated with public executioners—signified danger and led to social ostracism (McLeod, 1981; Omotoso, 2018; Sieber and Herreman, 2000). Gold adornments, often worn on the head and around the body in abundance, were central to Akan royalty aesthetics, so much so that

Portuguese colonists named the region the ‘Gold Coast’ after witnessing its cultural significance. A 14th-century Portuguese chronicler recounts this description of a king from the region:

His arms and legs were covered with chains and trinkets of gold in many shapes, and countless bells and large beads of gold were hanging from the hair of his beard and his head (Bennett, 2018, pp. 33)

Amongst the Akan and Ewe people, priest and priestess wore their hair in ‘mpesempese’ or dreadlocks. As shown in *Figure 2*, the style was given to children born to appeal to the gods, assigning them as future priests or priestesses. (Ngandu-Kalenga Greensword, 2022; Dabiri, 2019; Omotoso, 2018; Sieber and Herreman, 2000). The Akan saying, ‘obaa n’enyimiam nye ne tsirhwin’—meaning “the glory (pride) of a woman is in her hair” – further reflects the cultural significance of hair (Essel, 2017, as cited in Botsio et al., 2023). Aligning with this belief, during puberty rites for girls, maternal figures—often hairdressers—taught the importance of hair grooming, personal hygiene, and the social importance thereof (Essel, 2021). For the youth in traditional Ghanaian societies, education was very intimate and created a socio-cultural awareness that would allow for the preservation of traditional social structures.

Figure 2. A Komfo (‘god’) child, Ghana, 1933-1939. Photographed by Ernst Walter Ringwald between 1933 and 1939. Retrieved and reproduced with permission from Basel Mission Archives. Copyright © Basel Mission Archives.

Sumptuary Laws: Dress and Identity in Europe

From the reign of Edward III through the 1600s, England—like much of Europe—enforced sumptuary laws that regulated clothing based on religion, sex, and class (Ribeiro, 2003). Justified through Christianity, these laws dictated permissible colours, fabrics, and embellishments, reinforcing social hierarchies and restricting upward mobility (Carrithers, 2015; Phillips, 2007; Bethencourt, 2019). While sumptuary laws—rooted in social morals and religion—also existed in pre-colonial West African societies (Bennett, 2018), European colonial rule violently disrupted pre-colonial traditional structures.

Both Catholic and Protestant authorities in Europe linked luxury to moral vices like pride and immorality, using sumptuary laws to enforce religious and social distinctions (Carrithers, 2015). In medieval Europe, Jews and Muslims were required to wear identifying clothing under mandates like the Fourth Lateran Council of 1215 (Carrithers, 2015). In 14th-century England, servants and yeomen were barred from wearing gold or silver embroidery, privileges reserved for esquires and nobles (Phillips, 2007).

These regulatory practices extended to its colonies, including the Gold Coast (present-day Ghana), where they were the first European colonialist to settle in the region in 1471. Beyond trade and politics, the Portuguese introduced missionary schools that laid the foundation for Western education in the region. However, these early institutions were not merely sites of learning; they were tools of cultural imposition, foreshadowing the deeper colonial subjugation that would follow as European powers expanded their control. The imposition of Eurocentric sumptuary laws subjugated African people, imposing foreign social hierarchies and moral codes (Green, 2019).

COLONIAL SUBJUGATION OF BLACK HAIR IN EDUCATION

During the colonial period, missionary schools– supported by colonial governments and European churches– played a pivotal role in spreading Western education throughout the Gold Coast. This educational expansion was not straightforward and encountered significant resistance from local communities. Missionary schools served a small percentage of the population and remained exclusive for a majority of the colonial era (Aboagye, 2021). As colonial education expanded, its policies were recognised as a mechanism of "mental control," designed to colonise and "civilise" African people (Adjei, 2010; Khalifa et al., 2019; Nkrumah, 1943; Wiafe, 2021).

The Basel Evangelical Missionary School, established in 1828, emerged as a prominent colonial institution that expanded education access to female students (Martin, 1976; Pinto, 2019). Their approach was invasive: Indigenous children were removed from their families and placed in boarding schools, with the explicit goal of cultural assimilation and religious conversion (Pinto, 2019). European colonisers understood the cultural significance of traditional hairdressing as a marker of socio-cultural identity (Johnson and Bankhead, 2014; Sieber and Herreman, 2000), and they strategically used this understanding to undermine Indigenous cultural practices within missionary schools. Any traditional practices, such as hairstyling, were dismissed as "heathen" by Western colonisers (Wiafe, 2021). For example, school administration forced mpesempese wearers to cut their hair, an act that represented renunciation of their communal identity and religion through Christian conversion (Essel, 2021). In missionary boarding schools, students became physically and ideologically distant from their cultural upbringings (Pinto, 2019).

Figure 3. "Negerkinder in die Schule gehend" (African children going to school). Ghana. (n.d) Note. Retrieved and reproduced with permission from Basel Mission Archives on 23.11.2024. Copyright © Basel Mission Archives.

Figure 4. "Negerkinder lesend" (African children reading), Ghana. (n.d). Note. Retrieved and reproduced with permission from Basel Mission Archives on 23.11.2024. Copyright © Basel Mission Archives.

Figure 3 and *Figure 4* depict the idealised young African students. In these images, the students' appearances represent the missionary schools' approach to cultural erasure. *Figure 4* showcases female students, all uniformly dressed in European clothing with short, closely cut hair, devoid of any traditional adornment or hairstyles. The male students in *Figure 3* are also dressed in European-style clothing, with closely cropped hair. One student wears a Western-styled hat, a symbolic accessory that would later come to represent the "Indigenous elites" –Africans with Western education and values (Aissat and Djafri, 201; Essay, 2008; Macbeath, 2010 as cited in Kpessa-Whyte and Tsekpo, 2021).

Figure 5. "Mädchenanstalt Odumase" (Girls' Boarding School Odumase), Gold Coast, 1883-1888. Note: Retrieved and reproduced with permission from Basel Mission Archives on 23.11.2024. Copyright © Basel Mission Archives.

In addition to the significance of cutting hair as a symbol of disowning cultural traditions, it was used to distinguish 'Euro-African' (biracial) students from African students who came from Indigenous local communities (Antwi and Bonsu, 2024; Darkwa, 2021; Essel, 2021). In class photos from the Basel Missionary boarding school in Odumase, *Figure 5*, the Krobo youth are seen with short, shaved hair, while the Euro-African students, who were typically children of European men, have longer hair, styled in puffs or parted.

The strict enforcement of Western grooming standards in missionary schools was a continuation of European sumptuary traditions that had long been used to regulate appearance and enforce social hierarchies (Green, 2019). These laws were adapted to further racial and cultural domination, ensuring that African students were visually and psychologically distanced from their Indigenous identities. Missionary schools, such as the Basel Evangelical Missionary School, systematically undermined Indigenous cultural practices by enforcing European dress codes and hairstyles.

This control over students' physical appearance was a calculated strategy of assimilation. Echoing Fanon's (1952) critique of coloniality, Western-styled attire and grooming practices served as a "white mask" imposed upon students, stripping them of their traditions and reinforcing their subjugation within the colonial hierarchy. By policing hair and dress, colonial administrators and missionaries not only sought to erase Indigenous cultural identity but also to create clear distinctions between those who had internalised European values and those who had not. The regulation of Black hair in education was thus

not an arbitrary rule but a deliberate mechanism of colonial control, ensuring that African students were both physically and psychologically shaped into subjects of the colonial state.

POST-INDEPENDENCE HAIR POLITICS: NAVIGATING NATIONAL IDENTITY

Western education was limited to a small population until government reforms led to the expansion of schools in the early 20th century, which dramatically increased enrolment (Aboagye, 2021). As Western education expanded, cultural transformations became increasingly evident in personal aesthetics, with Omotoso (2018) describing the early years of globalisation in postcolonial societies as a period when hair became an object of 'cultural imperialism' (Omotoso, 2018, p. 11). Growing imports of Western media in the late 19th century catalysed the adoption of Western hairstyles among educated Ghanaians. Reflecting that Western aesthetics were becoming the norm amongst this population, students and those formally educated adopted a short, parted hairstyle known as *aboy* (Essah, 2008). *Figure 6* shows the *aboy* hairstyle on male and female students at the affluent Achimota College.

Figure 6. The son of Sylvanus Olympio, first President of Togo, with unnamed female pupil, Achimota School, 1957–1959. Note: Photographed by Winlaw, A. W. E. Provided by Cambridge University Library. Images are in copyright. All rights reserved.

The *aboy* hairstyle amongst students distinguished the Western-educated African student from non-Western-educated students. The students' choice to adopt this Eurocentric hairstyle reflects what Thiong'o describes as a "culture of apemanship and parrotry" (Thiong'o, 2019, p. 2). Yet, it was at no fault of their own. Colonial administrators made the adoption of Western hairstyles palatable by reframing them as a symbol of an elite social status, rather than an object of control. Traditional markers of heritage were obscured in students' appearances— being replaced by a symbol of Western educational attainment and idolisation. This transformation visually represented colonial knowledge systems erasing cultural identity.

Hats Off to Nkrumah

Kwame Nkrumah, a former student of the Achimota School, challenged conventions of the Western-educated aesthetic through his appearance. In *Fashioning the Nation: Hairdressing Professionalism and the Performance of Gender in Ghana, 1900-2006*, Essah (2008) refers to an article published in the *Accra Evening News*, titled "Hats off to Nkrumah" which presents Nkrumah as an Afro-centric leader who rejected colonial fashion norms – such as the top hat. Nkrumah challenged colonial ideals that equated sophistication with Western clothing and hairstyles by embracing traditional attire and wearing his hair in its natural state.

During Nkrumah's presidency, his educational reforms embodied tension between political liberation from British colonialist and internal cultural uniformity amongst the various communities. Nkrumah

sought to create a unified national identity through shifting educational policies (Pinto, 2024). This nation-building project was particularly crucial in rural northern areas that had been culturally and historically disconnected from the coastal and southern regions (Aboagye, 2021; Kpessa-Whyte and Tsekpó, 2021). Despite Nkrumah's personal rejection of colonial aesthetic norms, the educational system paradoxically retained colonial hair and dress code policies.

Mudimbe (1998) viewed Nkrumah's policies as the essentialising of various ethnic communities, as his ideals of unity under common identity inherently stemmed from Western epistemologies that viewed all African people as the same (Tsembo, 2022). Aligning with the views of Mudimbe (1998), in this era of postcolonialism, national education policies enacted what Sefa Dei terms "the colonising discourse of 'sameness'" – transforming schools into sites of cultural homogenisation (Sefa Dei, 2005, p. 70). Black African students continued to keep their hair short and inhabit boarding school to mask ethnic identities (Kpessa-Whyte and Tsekpó, 2021). The education system thus became a site where the rhetoric of creating a national identity was undermined by practices of ethnic cultural erasure, with hair serving as a medium of this—a dynamic that persists in contemporary Ghanaian public schools.

CONTEMPORARY CONTESTATIONS: ENFORCEMENT AND RESISTANCE

Colloquially termed *santo*, the mandated short buzz-cut style for Black African students represents a persistent mechanism of cultural suppression in contemporary times. Even hairstyles, similar to *aboy*, are subject to punitive disciplinary actions that disrupt students' education. In 2015, at St. John's Grammar Senior High School in Accra, three students were prohibited from taking the West African Senior School Certificate Exam (WASSCE) due to their 'bushy hair,' (see Figure 7), with school authorities citing previous policy infractions to justify their exclusion (CitiFm, 2015). The Director-General of the Ghana Education Service (GES), Jacob Kor, critiqued the school administration's actions— not for suppressing students' self-expression, but rather for the poorly timed nature of the incident (CitiFm, 2015).

Ernest Darkwa's (2021) study at St. Sebastian Senior High School in Adumasa, Ghana, further shows that such practices are not isolated incidents but represent an institutional norm. Darkwa's research revealed that students who deviate slightly from hair regulations face significant consequences, including potential suspension from school activities. The growing discourse among current and former students (Forson, 2019; Scallion, 1957, 2013; Yeboah, 2022) highlights various cases where contemporary hair politics in Ghana's public school system serve as a mechanism of control that negatively impacts students' academic experiences and personal development.

In 2019, Ghanaian actress and former student of Ghanaian public schools, Lydia Forson, took to Facebook to campaign for schools to allow Black African students to have agency over their hair. Forson recounts her experience of being forced to cut her hair as a schoolgirl in Ghana, sharing that she was informed by school administrators and people within her community that this rule was rooted in the belief that short hair helps students focus better on their studies. She questions the double standard that allowed white or foreign-born schoolgirls to keep their hair long while Black African girls were required to cut theirs (Pulse Ghana, 2019). This point of division and discrimination based on hair, brought up by Forson, is reminiscent of the hair politics imposed on Black African students during colonial education.

Echoing Forson's (2019, cited in Pulse Ghana, 2019) account, Faustina Yeboah (2022), a student at the Ghana Institute of Journalism, wrote a reflective piece, Dear Ghana Education Service (GES), my books have nothing to do with my hair, on her experience with hair politics in a Ghanaian senior high school. Yeboah recounts the embarrassment of having her hair trimmed by teachers in front of her peers and witnessing it happen to others in often humiliating ways. Despite justifications offered by administrators—aligning with the justification given to Forson (2019, cited in Pulse Ghana, 2019) and offered by Mensah (2023, cited in Dzivenu, 2023)—Yeboah argues that such practices are unnecessary and even traumatising. As a student, she was unable to vocalise her objections, recognising that questioning school administration would be perceived as an act of disobedience. In Darkwa's (2021) study, both male and female students also stated that they were uncomfortable with the policy on short hair but complied to stay in school. This shows how Ghanaian public schools perpetuate colonial power dynamics and homogenising nationalism by creating hierarchies that systematically silence and control students through punitive measures (Adzahlie-Mensah and Dunne, 2018; Kpessa-Whyte and Tsekpó, 2021).

The discriminatory nature of this policy extends beyond gender, affecting students from marginalised communities as well. This is exemplified by the case of Tyrone Iras Marhguy, a Rastafarian student who

was denied admission to the Achimota School due to his dreadlocks, a significant aspect of his faith (GhanaWeb, 2023). Despite a high court ruling in his favour, Achimota School continued to challenge the decision, revealing the persistence of cultural intolerance within public schools in Ghana. This intolerance stems from the postcolonial push for cultural 'sameness' in public schools, aimed at fostering national unity among Ghana's diverse ethnolinguistic groups (Kpessa-Whyte and Tsekpo, 2021; Nkrumah, 1943). As Sefa Dei (2005) argues, this emphasis on uniformity is rooted in post-independence efforts to consolidate a national identity, yet it mirrors colonial education ideals that viewed cultural 'difference' as disruptive. While colonial schools differentiated between Indigenous and mixed-race children—often privileging the latter—postcolonial education policies sought to erase such distinctions in favour of a homogenised national identity (Kpessa-Whyte and Tsekpo, 2021). However, in doing so, they continued to marginalise cultural expressions that deviated from the established norm, as seen in the Achimota case.

Figure 7. Image of the students barred from taking the WASSCE because of their “bushy hair.” Note. Courtesy of CitiFM Ghana.

Conflicting Perspectives on Current Hair Politics

There is a disconnect between how school administration perceives the effectiveness of current hair politics and the actuality of the students' experiences. Administrators like Alberta Mensah (2023, cited in Dzivenu, 2023) argue that policy on hair ensures simplicity, prevents distractions, and prepares students for structured working environments. When asked about the origins of current hair politics, students regurgitate these same arguments on why it is in place, yet show discontent for the policy (Manfo, 2018)

Ultimately, the issue of hair politics comes down to the school administration's perception of 'differences' within the educational setting (Adzahlie-Mensah and Dunne, 2018; Sefa Dei, 2005). Sefa Dei's (2005) study reveals that most administrators viewed difference as a potential source of conflict. This perspective is echoed by Mensah (2023, as cited in Dzivenu, 2023), who argues that variations in hairstyles could breed competition, leading to distractions within the learning environment. Adversely, administrators who advocate for embracing cultural differences and individual self-expression remain a marginal group, both ideologically and in terms of ethnic and gender representation (Aidoo, 2002; Sefa Dei, 2005).

Reconsidering Current Hair Politics

Forson (2019, as cited in Pulse Ghana, 2019) and Yeboah (2022) call for the Ghana Education Service (GES) to reconsider this outdated and discriminatory rule. In Manfo's (2018) study of female students in Labone Senior High School in Ghana, 81% of students disagreed with the administration's reasoning for the policy on hair, with 85% agreeing that long hair should be permitted. The growing population of students' rejection of this norm is a key step towards decolonising hair politics in public schools. Mignolo (2022) would describe students' questioning of current hair politics as an act of epistemic disobedience. Instead of blindly accepting the current hair politics, they challenge the idea that the state of their natural hair has anything to do with their studies.

In justifying the need for current hair politics, Mensah (2023, as cited in Dzivenu, 2023) offers some consolation to the current debate and recognises alternative practices that can meet the same outcomes intended by administration, such as having students wear their hair in *cornrows*. In Manfo's (2018) study, students stated that if given the opportunity, *cornrows* would be their hairstyle of choice in schools. This arrangement does not make schools more inclusive of differences nor fully recognise traditional and Indigenous hairstyles within school spaces. Yet, it instead reinforces a uniform aesthetic that effectively

polices students' self-expression – a continuation of Western educational systems that, from its origin, were never designed to support Black hair.

CONCLUSION

The origins of current hair politics in Ghana's public schools can be traced by observing the changing patterns of how Black hair has been perceived in educational institutions from pre-colonial to contemporary times. A decolonial framework brings attention to how hair politics rooted in colonialism affects cultural identity, historical power dynamics, and educational governance. During the colonial era, shaving the heads of Black African students was mandated to distinguish them from their mixed-race counterparts, reinforcing colonial ideals of social hierarchy (Wiafe, 2021). In the times nearing independence and after, the hair politics of colonial education systems aided in the formation of a national identity—once again decentering ethnic cultures and identities (Omotoso, 2018). Today, this practice endures as a means of uniformity that supposedly prevents distractions, with mixed-race and non-Black students continuing to be exempt. As the academic space has been unwelcoming to students' voices, students have taken to other mediums, such as social media, to express their concerns.

The Ghana Education Services has no provisions enforcing schools to make Black African students cut their hair, and simultaneously has no provisions protecting students from hair-related discrimination, as seen with Marghuy's legal battle against Achimota School (GhanaWeb, 2023). Due to the coloniality of hierarchies within schools, students feel disempowered to speak out against school administration—allowing for such injustices to continue (Antwi and Bonsu, 2024). There is a need for comprehensive policy reform on discipline in schools to dismantle hierarchical power structures left by colonialism. This would allow students to feel less like 'subjects', and more like active members of the school (Adzahlie-Mensah and Dunne, 2018).

Administrators need to be equipped to embrace differences and recognise cultural diversity as an educational strength, rather than a challenge to institutional norms. Sefa Dei (2005) emphasises that fostering inclusive school environments requires an anti-colonial approach to education—one that does not merely accommodate diversity but actively integrates Indigenous knowledge and cultural practices into pedagogy. In the context of hair politics, this means acknowledging the historical role of grooming policies in marginalising Black students and ensuring that school regulations on grooming do not reinforce colonial hierarchies but enforce traits of holistic well-being (e.g. shaving, caring for natural hair).

Similarly, Thiong'o (1986) argues that decolonising education involves rejecting Eurocentric standards as the default and creating space for discourse on Indigeneity in educational spaces. Applying this principle, administrators should engage with students, parents, and cultural historians to develop policies that affirm rather than suppress cultural identities. This could take the form of revising uniform codes to allow traditional hairstyles, incorporating studies of various local ethnolinguistic groups into school curricula, and fostering dialogue on the significance of self-expression situated in a historical context.

Ultimately, empowering students means giving them agency in their choice to connect with their cultural heritage without fear of institutional reprimand. By centring cultural diversity in educational policies, administrators can shift from a model of assimilation to one of genuine inclusion, creating learning environments where all students feel valued and affirmed in their identities. Until all these conditions are met, Ghana's public schools will remain sites of systemic cultural suppression, perpetuating colonial-era power dynamics that marginalise students' identities.

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